

Bridging the Gap Between Technical Validation and Societal Impact: Evidence from the Large-scale Edge Computing Piloting Project

Hazana Halimi
Kingston University London, UK

Youngseok Thomas Choi (Y.Choi@kingston.ac.uk)
Kingston University London, UK

Uthayasankar Sivarajah
Kingston University London, UK

Amizan Omar
University of Bradford, UK

Abstract

Edge computing is reshaping industrial operations, yet its adoption remains constrained by a shortage of validated frameworks for assessing impact beyond technical performance. Drawing on the COP-PILOT Horizon Europe project – a large-scale edge computing pilot involving 46 partners across four strategic sectors (energy, smart cities, agriculture, manufacturing) – this paper develops an integrated evaluation framework aligning Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) with Key Value Indicators (KVIs). Through a longitudinal, multi-sectoral co-operative inquiry, the study bridges technical validation and societal impact assessment, offering managers and policymakers a structured pathway for scaling value-centric edge-to-cloud solutions.

Keywords: Technical validation, Edge computing, Societal impact

Introduction

The rapid expansion of data-intensive industrial processes, autonomous decision-making, and cyber-physical integration has exposed the structural limitations of centralised cloud computing. Latency, bandwidth constraints, energy consumption, and growing data-sovereignty concerns are driving a fundamental shift towards decentralised, edge-centric architectures in which computation is pushed closer to the sources of data generation (Shi et al., 2016; Choi et al., 2022). Edge computing is increasingly regarded as the operational backbone of Industry 5.0, enabling real-time orchestration, resilience, and context-aware services across distributed production, logistics, and service environments (Breque et al., 2021). Despite this momentum, evidence on how edge-to-cloud continuums create value across technical, organisational, and societal dimensions remains fragmented, and the absence of validated assessment frameworks slows the transition of promising pilots into scaled adoption.

Operations management research on digital infrastructures has predominantly focused on the technical efficiencies of emerging technologies – latency reduction, bandwidth optimisation, throughput, and system reliability (Neely et al., 1995; Bititci et al., 2012). While these indicators remain necessary, they are increasingly insufficient in networked environments where value is co-created across heterogeneous actors and where outcomes extend to social, environmental, and ecosystem-level effects (Vargo and Lusch, 2016; Adner, 2017). Recent calls for socially relevant operations management (Sunar and Swaminathan, 2022) and for frameworks capturing the societal footprint of disruptive technologies (Choi et al., 2022) highlight a critical gap: engineering-centric validation captures whether a technology works, but not whether – and how – it creates meaningful value for stakeholders and society.

This paper addresses that gap by investigating how large-scale edge computing pilots can be evaluated in a way that reconciles technical performance with broader value creation. The empirical context is the COP-PILOT project, a Horizon Europe large-scale pilot involving 46 partners and four industrial piloting clusters spanning energy, smart cities, agriculture, and manufacturing. COP-PILOT represents one of the largest European initiatives dedicated to orchestrating edge-to-cloud services across multiple strategic sectors, providing a uniquely rich setting to examine how heterogeneous technologies, stakeholders, and operational logics interact.

The study pursues two research questions. First, how can performance measurement in large-scale edge computing pilots be extended to capture ecosystem and societal value alongside technical efficiency? Second, what mechanisms enable such evaluation to translate into actionable guidance for managers and policymakers navigating high-uncertainty technology transitions? To answer these questions, we develop an integrated KPI–KVI framework grounded in Service-Dominant Logic, Socio-Technical Systems theory, and platform ecosystem research, and we operationalise it through a four-phase, co-operative inquiry process across the COP-PILOT clusters.

The paper makes three contributions. Academically, it advances technology management and performance measurement theory by articulating a value-oriented evaluation framework specifically designed for infrastructures characterised by acute technological uncertainty. Practically, it equips managers with a toolkit for mitigating the “valley of death” associated with piloting unproven technologies and provides early evidence that orchestrated edge-to-cloud services can deliver substantial operational and environmental gains. From a policy perspective, the work offers an evidence base for future European regulatory and standardisation agendas in decentralised intelligence.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. The next section reviews the literature on performance measurement in digital and platform-based environments and identifies the theoretical foundations of the proposed framework. We then describe the methodology and the COP-PILOT research setting, before presenting the integrated evaluation framework and preliminary cross-cluster insights. A discussion of contributions and implications follows, and the paper concludes by outlining limitations and avenues for further research.

Literature review: beyond technical efficiency in digital platform evaluation

Developing a robust framework for evaluating edge computing pilots requires revisiting the assumptions underlying performance measurement in operations management and extending them towards a value-oriented perspective. Traditional approaches have emphasised efficiency, control, and optimisation within organisational boundaries (Neely et al., 1995; Bititci et al., 2012), yet contemporary digital environments increasingly demand evaluation mechanisms that capture multi-actor interactions and

system-level outcomes (Jacobides et al., 2018; Constantinides et al., 2018). We draw on three complementary perspectives – the critique of KPI-centric evaluation, Service-Dominant Logic and Key Value Indicators, and Socio-Technical Systems with platform generativity – to ground the evaluation framework developed in this study.

The dominance and limitations of KPI-centric evaluation

Performance measurement has long been anchored in efficiency- and control-oriented metrics. Neely, Gregory and Platts (1995) define it as “the process of quantifying the efficiency and effectiveness of action”, and early frameworks emphasised quantitative indicators such as cost, throughput, utilisation, and cycle time (Kaplan and Norton, 1992). These approaches are closely aligned with Product-Dominant (P-D) logic, in which value is conceptualised as embedded in outputs and realised at the point of exchange (Vargo and Lusch, 2016). In digital and platform-based environments this orientation translates into infrastructure-level indicators – throughput, latency, system uptime, and processing capacity – that serve as proxies for technical performance (Bourne et al., 2000). While essential for reliability and scalability, such metrics remain confined to the technological artefact itself, offering limited insight into how value emerges through interactions among stakeholders (Ng and Vargo, 2018; Yoo et al., 2010).

Service-Dominant Logic and Key Value Indicators

Service-Dominant (S-D) Logic reframes value as co-created through the integration of resources by multiple actors and as uniquely determined by its beneficiary (Vargo and Lusch, 2016; Chandler and Vargo, 2011). In this view, value is realised in use and is therefore context-dependent and experiential, requiring evaluation frameworks that capture how platforms enable capability development, innovation, and interaction quality across actors (Edvardsson et al., 2011; Akaka and Vargo, 2014). Digital platforms do not merely deliver services; they facilitate resource integration by connecting actors, capabilities, and data across organisational boundaries (Lusch and Nambisan, 2015), so performance must be read at the ecosystem level (Adner, 2017). Building on this, the concept of Key Value Indicators (KVIs) has been proposed as an explicit extension to KPIs, aiming to make value creation measurable across economic, relational, and societal dimensions (Wikström et al., 2024). Whereas KPIs capture system performance, KVIs assess how digital infrastructures enable outcomes such as collaboration, trust, innovation, and sustainability, thereby offering a structured mechanism for linking technical capabilities with ecosystem-level value.

Socio-technical systems and platform generativity

Socio-Technical Systems (STS) theory emphasises that effective systems emerge from the joint functioning of social and technical components rather than from technological optimisation alone (Trist and Bamforth, 1951; Cherno, 1976; Pasmore et al., 1982). Applied to digital infrastructures, STS suggests that the performance of an edge-to-cloud platform depends on the alignment of technical architectures with organisational structures, governance arrangements, and stakeholder practices (Tiwana et al., 2010; Nambisan et al., 2017). Complementarily, research on platform ecosystems stresses generativity – the capacity of a technological system to produce unprompted change driven by varied and distributed audiences (Zittrain, 2006) – as a defining feature of value creation. In generative ecosystems, orchestration and governance mechanisms determine how resources are recombined, how innovation is coordinated, and how value is distributed across participants (Tiwana, 2014; Cusumano et al., 2019). For large-scale edge computing pilots such as COP-PILOT, these perspectives imply that evaluation

must simultaneously address technical robustness, socio-organisational integration, and the generative potential of the infrastructure across sectors.

Synthesising these perspectives, the literature points to a clear need for evaluation approaches that combine efficiency-oriented KPIs with value-oriented KVI, and that frame platform performance as an emergent, socio-technical, and ecosystem-level phenomenon. Addressing this need is particularly urgent for decentralised intelligence infrastructures such as edge-to-cloud continuums, where heterogeneous stakeholders, uncertain technologies, and societal expectations intersect. In response, this study develops and applies an integrated KPI–KVI framework tailored to large-scale edge computing pilots.

Design and Methodology

The study adopts a longitudinal, multi-disciplinary research design centred on the COP-PILOT project, a Horizon Europe large-scale pilot involving 46 partners across four industrial piloting clusters – energy, smart cities, agriculture, and manufacturing. This multi-sectoral breadth supports rich cross-comparisons and strengthens the theoretical coverage of value assessment beyond a single-industry focus, while allowing the research to engage with the complexities of socio-technical systems in which social and technical elements must be co-designed for effective performance (Cherns, 1976).

The methodology follows a four-phase cycle combining requirements engineering, framework development, co-operative inquiry, and impact assessment. Phase 1 extracts functional and non-functional requirements from heterogeneous stakeholders, including technology providers, industrial end-users, public authorities, and citizen-oriented intermediaries. Grounded in stakeholder theory (Freeman, 2010), this phase ensures that requirements capture the needs of both primary and secondary actors and mitigate risks of misalignment. Phase 2 develops a hierarchical validation framework that aligns technical KPIs with broader KVI, reflecting the transition towards Industry 5.0 principles in which operations are evaluated on efficiency, human-centricity, and societal resilience (Breque et al., 2021).

Phase 3 operationalises a “co-operative inquiry” in which technology developers and industrial end-users engage in iterative, real-world testing. In an operations context, this functions as action research, where researchers and practitioners collaborate to solve immediate operational problems while simultaneously contributing to theory (Coughlan and Coughlan, 2002). Data collection spans multiple waves across the project lifecycle and combines semi-structured interviews with cluster leaders and domain experts, structured self-assessment instruments completed by each pilot, documentary analysis of technical and reporting deliverables, and direct observation of integration workshops. Phase 4 synthesises this evidence into a sustainability and business impact assessment that adopts a triple bottom line perspective (Elkington, 1998; Pagell and Wu, 2009), ensuring that technological interventions are examined for long-term economic viability alongside environmental and social benefits.

Cross-cluster analysis follows Eisenhardt's (1989) logic of theory-building from cases, using within-case analysis to characterise each cluster's specific evaluation profile, followed by cross-case pattern matching to surface common and sector-specific indicators. Coding is performed iteratively against the KPI–KVI hierarchy, with indicators refined through successive validation workshops with consortium partners. The resulting framework is therefore both theoretically informed and empirically grounded in the lived experience of a large-scale European edge computing initiative.

An integrated KPI–KVI framework for edge computing pilots

The framework developed from the COP-PILOT engagements organises evaluation along three interlinked layers. The first, technical performance, captures conventional KPIs such as latency, availability, energy efficiency per workload, and orchestration overhead – indicators that remain essential for demonstrating infrastructure readiness. The second, operational and ecosystem value, captures KVIs relating to cross-partner collaboration, interoperability, reusability of components across sectors, and the extent to which the platform enables new services built by third parties. The third, societal and sustainability impact, captures KVIs relating to resource and carbon footprint reduction, digital inclusion, support for public services, and alignment with European strategic autonomy objectives.

Table 1 summarises representative indicators derived from cross-cluster analysis. Each pilot contributes domain-specific nuances – for example, peak-shaving and demand-response indicators in energy; air-quality and mobility indicators in smart cities; water-use and yield indicators in agriculture; and overall equipment effectiveness in manufacturing – while sharing a common backbone of platform-level KPIs and ecosystem-level KVIs.

Table 1 – Integrated KPI–KVI framework for edge computing pilots

Layer	Focus	Representative indicators
Technical performance (KPIs)	Infrastructure readiness of the edge-to-cloud continuum	Latency; availability; energy efficiency per workload; orchestration overhead; cyber-resilience
Operational & ecosystem value (KVIs)	Cross-partner value creation and platform generativity	Interoperability; component reusability across sectors; number and diversity of third-party services; time-to-onboard new partners
Societal & sustainability impact (KVIs)	Contribution to societal, environmental, and strategic objectives	Carbon footprint reduction; resource efficiency; digital inclusion; quality of public services; European digital sovereignty alignment
Governance & learning (cross-cutting)	Joint optimisation of social and technical elements	Stakeholder engagement depth; speed of issue resolution; knowledge-transfer events; cumulative lessons learned

Preliminary cross-cluster analysis produces three patterns. First, pilots that achieve strong KPI performance do not automatically deliver high KVI scores; interoperability, governance clarity, and end-user engagement are decisive in translating technical performance into ecosystem value. Second, KVIs anchored in societal impact – particularly carbon footprint reduction and public-service quality – act as boundary objects that align the heterogeneous interests of technology providers, end-users, and public authorities within the consortium. Third, the framework surfaces a “valley of death” between technical validation and scaled deployment that is primarily organisational rather than technological: pilots stall where KVIs have not been made explicit, measurable, or shared across partners. Making KVIs first-class citizens

alongside KPIs thus emerges as a prerequisite for turning promising demonstrations into durable industrial deployments.

Discussion and contribution

The contribution of this research is three-fold. Academically, the study advances technology management and performance measurement theory by integrating Service-Dominant Logic, Socio-Technical Systems, and platform generativity into a coherent KPI–KVI framework tailored to decentralised intelligence infrastructures. It responds to calls for socially relevant operations management (Sunar and Swaminathan, 2022) and addresses the gap identified by Choi et al. (2022) regarding the absence of proven methodologies for measuring the societal and sustainability footprints of disruptive technologies. By defining verifiable indicators for cross-sector collaboration – including resource optimisation, carbon footprint reduction, and enhanced social services – the framework provides a theoretical bridge between technical validation and organisational value creation.

Practically, the findings equip managers with a toolkit for mitigating the “valley of death” associated with piloting unproven technologies. The multi-sectoral evidence demonstrates how structured performance measurement can reduce the perceived risks of technological uncertainty, enabling firms to scale decentralised solutions with greater confidence. The preliminary results indicate that orchestrated edge-to-cloud services can lead to meaningful reductions in operational expenditure and idle resource consumption, thereby enhancing both industrial competitiveness and environmental performance. Managers in sectors undergoing digital transformation can deploy the framework to sequence investments, identify governance gaps, and make explicit trade-offs between speed and value-centric design.

From a policy perspective, COP-PILOT represents one of the largest EU-funded initiatives in decentralised intelligence and therefore provides a vital evidence base for future regulatory frameworks. The study highlights the necessity of standardised interfacing protocols to prevent market fragmentation and suggests that policy interventions should increasingly reward value-centric innovation. By documenting the challenges and successes of these pilots, the work informs policymakers on the infrastructure investments and standardisation efforts required to maintain European leadership in the global digital economy.

Conclusion

This paper develops an integrated KPI–KVI evaluation framework for large-scale edge computing pilots and illustrates its application across the four sectoral clusters of the COP-PILOT Horizon Europe project. By combining Service-Dominant Logic, Socio-Technical Systems theory, and platform ecosystem perspectives, the framework offers a systematic means of bridging technical validation and societal impact. The study is subject to limitations: it draws on early-stage pilot evidence, and the KVI measurement instruments will continue to mature as the consortium completes its validation cycles. Future research will extend the framework through deeper quantitative benchmarking across clusters, comparative analysis with non-European pilots, and longitudinal evaluation of post-project adoption trajectories. Taken together, the work offers an actionable contribution to operations management scholarship and a practical decision-support instrument for managers and policymakers navigating the transition to decentralised, value-centric digital infrastructures.

References

- Adner, R. (2017), "Ecosystem as structure: an actionable construct for strategy", *Journal of Management*, Vol. 43 No. 1, pp. 39–58.
- Akaka, M.A. and Vargo, S.L. (2014), "Technology as an operant resource in service (eco)systems", *Information Systems and e-Business Management*, Vol. 12 No. 3, pp. 367–384.
- Bititci, U.S., Garengo, P., Dörfler, V. and Nudurupati, S.S. (2012), "Performance measurement: challenges for tomorrow", *International Journal of Management Reviews*, Vol. 14 No. 3, pp. 305–327.
- Bourne, M., Mills, J., Wilcox, M., Neely, A. and Platts, K. (2000), "Designing, implementing and updating performance measurement systems", *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, Vol. 20 No. 7, pp. 754–771.
- Breque, M., De Nul, L. and Petridis, A. (2021), Industry 5.0: Towards a Sustainable, Human-Centric and Resilient European Industry, European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Luxembourg.
- Chandler, J.D. and Vargo, S.L. (2011), "Contextualisation and value-in-context: how context frames exchange", *Marketing Theory*, Vol. 11 No. 1, pp. 35–49.
- Cherns, A. (1976), "The principles of sociotechnical design", *Human Relations*, Vol. 29 No. 8, pp. 783–792.
- Choi, T.M., Kumar, S., Yue, X. and Chan, H.L. (2022), "Disruptive technologies and operations management in the Industry 4.0 era and beyond", *Production and Operations Management*, Vol. 31 No. 1, pp. 9–31.
- Constantinides, P., Henfridsson, O. and Parker, G.G. (2018), "Introduction – platforms and infrastructures in the digital age", *Information Systems Research*, Vol. 29 No. 2, pp. 381–400.
- Coughlan, P. and Coughlan, D. (2002), "Action research for operations management", *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, Vol. 22 No. 2, pp. 220–240.
- Cusumano, M.A., Gawer, A. and Yoffie, D.B. (2019), *The Business of Platforms: Strategy in the Age of Digital Competition, Innovation, and Power*, Harper Business, New York.
- Edvardsson, B., Tronvoll, B. and Gruber, T. (2011), "Expanding understanding of service exchange and value co-creation", *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, Vol. 39 No. 2, pp. 327–339.
- Eisenhardt, K.M. (1989), "Building theories from case study research", *Academy of Management Review*, Vol. 14 No. 4, pp. 532–550.
- Elkington, J. (1998), *Cannibals with Forks: The Triple Bottom Line of 21st Century Business*, New Society Publishers, Gabriola Island.
- Freeman, R.E. (2010), *Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- Jacobides, M.G., Cennamo, C. and Gawer, A. (2018), "Towards a theory of ecosystems", *Strategic Management Journal*, Vol. 39 No. 8, pp. 2255–2276.
- Kaplan, R.S. and Norton, D.P. (1992), "The balanced scorecard: measures that drive performance", *Harvard Business Review*, Vol. 70 No. 1, pp. 71–79.
- Lusch, R.F. and Nambisan, S. (2015), "Service innovation: a service-dominant logic perspective", *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 39 No. 1, pp. 155–175.
- Nambisan, S., Lyytinen, K., Majchrzak, A. and Song, M. (2017), "Digital innovation management: reinventing innovation management research in a digital world", *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 41 No. 1, pp. 223–238.
- Neely, A., Gregory, M. and Platts, K. (1995), "Performance measurement system design: a literature review and research agenda", *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, Vol. 15 No. 4, pp. 80–116.
- Ng, I.C.L. and Vargo, S.L. (2018), "Service-dominant (S-D) logic, service ecosystems and institutions: bridging theory and practice", *Journal of Service Management*, Vol. 29 No. 4, pp. 518–520.
- Pagell, M. and Wu, Z. (2009), "Building a more complete theory of sustainable supply chain management using case studies of 10 exemplars", *Journal of Supply Chain Management*, Vol. 45 No. 2, pp. 37–56.
- Pasmore, W., Francis, C., Haldeman, J. and Shani, A. (1982), "Sociotechnical systems: a North American reflection on empirical studies of the seventies", *Human Relations*, Vol. 35 No. 12, pp. 1179–1204.
- Shi, W., Cao, J., Zhang, Q., Li, Y. and Xu, L. (2016), "Edge computing: vision and challenges", *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, Vol. 3 No. 5, pp. 637–646.
- Sunar, N. and Swaminathan, J.M. (2022), "Socially relevant and inclusive operations management", *Production and Operations Management*, Vol. 31 No. 12, pp. 4379–4392.

- Tiwana, A. (2014), *Platform Ecosystems: Aligning Architecture, Governance, and Strategy*, Morgan Kaufmann, Waltham, MA.
- Tiwana, A., Konsynski, B. and Bush, A.A. (2010), “Research commentary – platform evolution: coevolution of platform architecture, governance and environmental dynamics”, *Information Systems Research*, Vol. 21 No. 4, pp. 675–687.
- Trist, E.L. and Bamforth, K.W. (1951), “Some social and psychological consequences of the Longwall method of coal-getting”, *Human Relations*, Vol. 4 No. 1, pp. 3–38.
- Vargo, S.L. and Lusch, R.F. (2016), “Institutions and axioms: an extension and update of service-dominant logic”, *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, Vol. 44 No. 1, pp. 5–23.
- Wikström, G., Bledow, N., Matinmikko-Blue, M., Breuer, H., Costa, C., Darzanos, G., Gavras, A., Hossfeld, T., Mesogiti, I., Petersen, K. and Porambage, P. (2024), “Key value indicators: a framework for values-driven next-generation ICT solutions”, *Telecommunications Policy*, Vol. 48 No. 6, 102778.
- Yoo, Y., Henfridsson, O. and Lyytinen, K. (2010), “Research commentary: the new organising logic of digital innovation”, *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 34 No. 4, pp. 724–735.
- Zittrain, J. (2006), “The generative Internet”, *Harvard Law Review*, Vol. 119 No. 7, pp. 1974–2040.